

Standard Heats of Formation of Uranyl(II) and Thorium(IV) Oxinates

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Manuscript received 6 April 1993, revised 10 February 1994, accepted 28 April 1994

Thermochemical studies of oxine or substituted oxine complexes have been scantily reported. For a number of oxinate complexes with divalent ions, the enthalpies of precipitation in aqueous phase have been studied¹.

The present communication deals with the thermochemical studies of uranyl(II) and thorium(IV) oxinates. The heats of combustion (ΔH_c) of the compounds have been measured by the use of static oxygen bomb calorimeter. By substituting the auxiliary thermochemical data, their standard heats of formation (ΔH_f°) have been estimated. These data have been used in the derivation of metal-nitrogen (ligand) bond strengths.

Results and Discussion

The heats of combustion of the compounds have been determined from the relation,

$$\Delta H_c = M W \Delta t$$

where M is the gram molecular weight of the crystalline compound, W the water equivalent of bomb calorimeter (measured as $10\,545 \pm 15 \text{ J K}^{-1}$) and Δt the temperature rise per gram of the sample due to bomb calorimetric combustion. As a result of combustion the following products were characterised²,

For these reactions, $\Delta H = \Delta H_c$. The percentage of residue in the calorimeter as a result of combustion coincided with that of the respective metal oxide for each oxinate compound.

The standard heats of formation of compounds were determined,

$$\Delta H_f^\circ \text{UO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON}(c) = 1/3 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{U}_3\text{O}_8(c) + 27 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{CO}_2(g) + 19/2 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{H}_2\text{O}(l) - \Delta H_c$$

$$\Delta H_f^\circ \text{Th}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON}(c) = \Delta H_f^\circ \text{ThO}_2(c) + 45 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{CO}_2(g) + 31/2 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{H}_2\text{O}(l) - \Delta H_c$$

The ΔH_f° values for $\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2$ and $\text{Th}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_4$ in crystalline forms have been estimated (Table 1) by knowing the ΔH_f° value for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ON}(c)$ ³ (-87 kJ mol^{-1}). The ΔH_f° (std.) values taken from the literature⁴ are -3576 , -1222 , -393.5 and $-285.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for $\text{U}_3\text{O}_8(c)$, $\text{ThO}_2(c)$, $\text{CO}_2(g)$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O}(l)$ respectively.

Estimation of metal-nitrogen bond strengths: The bond energy terms for crystalline $\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2$ and $\text{Th}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_4$ were determined respectively as

$$\Delta H_g = \Delta H_f^\circ (\text{cryst.}) + \Delta H_{\text{sub}} - \Delta H_f^\circ \text{UO}_2(g) - 2 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON}(g)$$

$$\Delta H_g = \Delta H_f^\circ (\text{cryst.}) + \Delta H_{\text{sub}} - \Delta H_f^\circ \text{Th}(g) - 4 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON}(g)$$

The heat of sublimation (ΔH_{sub}) is assumed to be close to that of respective metal chloride⁴. The heat of formation of gaseous oxine is 21 kJ mol^{-1} (Ref. 2). The ΔH_f° value for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON}(g)$ was estimated from the phenolic O-H bond dissociation energy (352 kJ mol^{-1}) and standard heat of formation of H atom (218 kJ mol^{-1}). The $\Delta H_f^\circ \text{UO}_2(g)$ and $\Delta H_f^\circ \text{Th}(g)$ values are -466 and -598 kJ mol^{-1} respectively³. The M-N bond strengths are estimated from the equations,

$$\Delta H_g = 2E(\text{UO}_2\text{-O}_{\text{lig.}}) + 2E(\text{UO}_2\text{-N}_{\text{lig.}})$$

TABLE 1 – THERMOCHEMICAL DATA OF URANYL(II) AND THORIUM(IV) OXINATES

Compd	Δt °C/g	ΔH_c kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH_f° kJ mol ⁻¹	$E(M-O)$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$E(M-N)$ kJ mol ⁻¹
UO ₂ (C ₉ H ₆ ON) ₂ C ₉ H ₇ ON	1 750+0 009	-12 997+10	-1 535	—	—
Th(C ₉ H ₆ ON) ₄ C ₉ H ₇ ON	2 162+0 008	-21 803+8	-1 562	—	—
UO ₂ (C ₉ H ₆ ON) ₂	—	—	-1 448	251	270
Th(C ₉ H ₆ ON) ₄	—	—	-1 475	296	324

$$\text{and } \Delta H_g = 4E(\text{Th}-\text{O}_{\text{lig}}) + 4E(\text{Th}-\text{N}_{\text{lig}})$$

The $E(M-O)$ values in the above equation have been taken from standard source³ (Table 1).

Experimental

Reagents of analytical grade were used for the preparation of the crystalline compounds⁵. Aqueous solutions of uranyl and thorium nitrates were treated with 2% alcoholic solution of oxine and ammonium hydroxide solution was added dropwise to these solutions for precipitation of the oxinate crystals. The oxinates were dried at room temperature.

The heat of combustion of each compound was determined in a bomb calorimeter by burning a weighed pellet of the sample in excess of oxygen and measuring the temperature rise in known quantity of water. The bomb calorimeter was standardised by burning certified grade benzoic acid and its water equivalent (W) was determined.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Professor Lambodar Thakur, Bhagalpur University, for discussion.

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